

Synthesis, spectral and antifungal studies of some iron(II,III) and cobalt(II) complexes of 4-amino-3-ethyl-5-mercapto-S-triazole

R. N. Sharma*, (Ms.) Poonam Giri, Amritesh Kumar^a, (Ms.) Alpana Kumari and R. N. Pandey^b

Department of Chemistry, K. N. Govt. P.G. College, Gyanpur, Sant Ravidas Nagar, Bhadohi-221 304, Uttar Pradesh, India

^aRMCH, Ranchi, Jharkhand, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, College of Commerce, Patna-800 020, Bihar, India

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Abstract : 4-Amino-3-ethyl-5-mercapto-S-triazole forms some air stable complexes with Fe^{II,III} and Co^{II} ions. All complexes are characterized through elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, electronic and infra red spectral studies. All complexes are six coordinated and tentatively octahedral structures has been assigned. 10 *Dq*, *B'* and β values for Co^{II} complexes indicate the strong ligand nature in spectrochemical series. All complexes have been screened against *Aspergillus flavus* and all exhibits significant antifungal activities.

Keywords : Iron(II,III), cobalt(II), triazole, antifungal studies.

In the present paper, the synthesis, characterization and antifungal activities of the complexes of 4-amino-3-ethyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (AEMTH) with the Fe^{II,III} and Co^{II} ions are described.

Results and discussion

A number of air stable Fe^{II,III} and Co^{II} complexes have been synthesized with AEMTH and pyridine ligands. 4-Amino-3-ethyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (AEMTH) tautomerized in thiol as well as thione form as shown below :

The complexes, their colour, decomposition temperature, conductance, analytical and IR and electronic spectral data are given in Table 1. Antifungal screening as average percentage inhibition data against *Aspergillus flavus* after 96 h have been given in Table 2. The measured μ_{eff} values (Table 1) of the complexes are in agree-

ment with the spin only value for corresponding metal ions. μ_{eff} values for Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes are good agreement with spin only value expected for high spin octahedral complexes may be due to metal interaction¹. The present data are good agreement with low spin octahedral configuration for all Co^{II} complexes with AEMTH. It is further supported by high β values (Table 2) for all Co^{II} complexes which are calculated from electronic spectral data.

The 10 *Dq*, *B'* and β values for all Co^{II} complexes have been calculated and are given in Table 2. These values suggest that the ligand is in the higher end of the spectrochemical series. All Fe^{II,III} and Co^{II} complexes show octahedral configuration².

Antibacterial activity : AEMTH and all other Fe^{II,III} and Co^{II} complexes were screened for their antifungal activities against *Aspergillus flavus* species at 10100 and 1000 ppm concentration for about 96 h inhibition. The solvent used was DMSO. The inhibition zone formed around each filter paper after inoculation for 96 h at room temperature were measured. The results were shown in Table 2. The standard fungicide used for comparison was carbendazim³. All the Fe^{II,III} and Co^{II} complexes exhibits significant antifungal activities. The bioactivities for complexes increase with increase in concentration. [Fe(AEMTH)(NO₃)₃(H₂O)₂] showed 91.3% activities

Table 1. Analytical, physical and spectral data of complexes

Complexes (colour)	pH of isolation	M.p (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Δn (Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	vNH vSH	vSO ₄ vNO ₃	Thioamide band (cm^{-1})				Electronic data (nm)	Assignment	
			C	H	N					I	II	III	IV			
AEMTH	7	144	33.33 (33.08)	0.06 (0.05)	38.9 (38.40)	-	-	3260 3210	-	1570	1390	1050	770	255	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ C.T.	
[Fe(AEMTH)(H ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃) ₃] (Leaf brown)	8	290	10.85 (11.37)	2.31 (2.48)	23.10 (23.22)	5.54	5.03	3310 3230	-	1495 1370	1575 1375	1630	750	245	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ C.T.	
[Fe(AEMTH)(Py)(H ₂ O)(NO ₃) ₃] (Brown)	9	> 290	21.67 (22.26)	2.60 (3.11)	23.05 (23.19)	5.71	3.38	3060 3765	-	1490 1370	1575 1370	1035	740	235	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ C.T.	
[Fe(AEMTH)(Py)(H ₂ O) ₄] ₂ SO ₄ (Leaf brown)	8	> 300	23.37 (24.16)	3.12 (4.70)	15.23 (15.66)	5.97	56.13	3070 3580	-	1114	1570	1380	1040	745	242	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ C.T.
[Co(AEMTH) ₂ (SO ₄)(H ₂ O) ₃] (Brandy)	6	> 300	19.10 (19.32)	3.15 (4.43)	22.34 (22.54)	1.52	7.35	3590 3210	-	1113	1580	1370	1035	750	245	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}(F)$
[Co(AEMTH) ₂ (Py)(H ₂ O) ₃] ₂ SO ₄ (Gray)	8	> 300	26.43 (27.08)	4.24 (4.69)	20.74 (21.88)	1.73	57.62	3730 3230	-	1113	1575	1380	1040	750	248	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}(F)$
[Co(AEMTH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] ₂ ac ₂ (Leaf brown)	6	> 300	25.19 (26.22)	4.93 (5.59)	20.22 (20.85)	1.63	165.02	3480 3370	-	1560	1575	1380	1030	745	240	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}(F)$
[Co(AEMTH)(Py)(H ₂ O) ₄] ₂ ac ₂ (Red)	8	180	22.15 (22.88)	4.32 (5.72)	13.80 (14.83)	1.52	159.76	3550 3210	-	1580	1570	1385	1035	740	245	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}(F)$
[Co(AEMTH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₃] (Gray)	6	> 300	22.45 (23.02)	4.83 (5.28)	25.31 (26.86)	1.52	5.69	3610 3340	-	-	1580	1375	1040	745	248	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}(F)$
[Co(AEMTH)(Py)(H ₂ O) ₃] (French blue)	8	180	30.32 (30.68)	4.15 (5.40)	13.32 (19.89)	1.80	6.33	3750 3210	-	-	1575	1370	1030	750	248	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$ $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}(F)$
							3060								690	$4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}(F)$

Table 2. Spectral and biological activities

Complexes	Nephelauxetic constant			Fungicidal activity Average % inhibition <i>A. flavus</i> (ppm)		
	10 Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B'	β	1000	100	10
	[Fe(AEMTH)(H ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃) ₃]	-	-	-	91.3	86.0
[Fe(AEMTH)(Py)(H ₂ O)(NO ₃) ₃]	-	-	-	60.0	51.7	44.1
[Fe(AEMTH)(Py)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄	-	-	-	58.3	42.5	37.0
[Co(AEMTH) ₂ (SO ₄)(H ₂ O) ₃]	9828	702	0.63	38.1	25.5	18.3
[Co(AEMTH) ₂ (Py)(H ₂ O) ₃]SO ₄	9842	702	0.63	40.0	25.0	20.0
[Co(AEMTH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]ac ₂	10000	702	0.64	36.4	22.7	17.9
[Co(AEMTH)(Py)(H ₂ O) ₄]ac ₂	9739	696	0.62	39.5	24.0	21.1
[CoO(AEMTH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₃]	9739	696	0.62	35.6	27.9	17.7
[CoO(AEMTH)(Py)(H ₂ O) ₃]	9825	702	0.63	45.9	32.4	20.0
Carbendazim	-	-	-	98.6	88.7	81.8

against *A. flavus* on comparison with carbendazim and may be treated as very strong antifungal agent. It may be due to presence of Fe^{II} and bioactive nitrate group. The exceptional activities may be also due to donor sulphur atom bonded with metal ions⁴. [Fe(AEMTH)(NO₃)₃(Py)(H₂O)] and [Fe(AEMTH)(Py)(H₂O)₄]SO₄ complexes may be assumed as moderate type of fungicides. All other Co^{II} complexes may be treated as a very weak type of fungicide.

Experimental

All chemicals used were C.P. grade. The ligand, 4-amino-3-ethyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (AEMTH) was prepared by some modified method reported in literature⁵. It was recrystallized from water-ethanol (1 : 1) solution (yield 60%).

All Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes were prepared in ethanol using general method⁶. But Co^{II} complexes were prepared in water. For cobalt complexes (5 mmol) sulphate and acetate salts are used and mixed with 50 ml ethanolic solution of ligand (10 mmol) and refluxed for about 2 h with few drops of corresponding mineral acids on sand bath. The pH of the mixture was adjusted as desired. It was evaporated to 10 ml and thereafter ice cooled. The crystals were separated and filtered. For pyridyl cobalt complexes, 10 ml pyridine was mixed into filtrate of corresponding salt complexes and again refluxed for 2 h at pH 7-8. The complexes were washed with (1 : 1) H₂O-EtOH mixture and the dried in a desiccator.

Elemental analysis was carried out at CDRI, Lucknow. Metal and sulphur were determined gravimetrically. Conductance measurements were carried out on digital con-

trol Dynamics (APX 185) conductivity meter. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made using a Gouy balance at RT using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as calibrant. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMF on Beckmann UV-spectrophotometer. The IR spectra of the ligand and complexes were taken on Jasco FT/IR-5300 spectrophotometer using KBr discs.

The antifungal activities were measured on cup plate methods reported in literature⁷.

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